

Legal aspects of HET: France

[WP3 – Human enhancement]

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Executive summary

On the basis of the overview presented in this report on the legal responses to HETs in France, it appears that issues and questions related to these technologies are rather weakly addressed by French legal experts. According to the authors of this report, this is primarily due to the ideological approach of the debate that tends to dominate in France. Indeed, discussions on HETs are immediately linked to transhumanism, which is an ideology that the French population rather massively rejects as, in France, it is linked to eugenics. Nonetheless, some legal experts have engaged with these issues and French positive law in its current form does provide some legal boundaries that are of particular relevance to the regulation of HETs.

A key element for the regulation of these technologies in France relates to the fact that French law, through the 1994 bioethics law, confers the human body a dignity. Accordingly, though the body has the legal status of an object, it is not any kind of object: it is “inviolable” (art. 16-1 of the Civil code). There may be “infringement of the integrity of the human body” only in cases of “medical necessity for the person or exceptionally in the therapeutic interest of another” (art. 16-1 of the Civil code). As some experts have argued, this position would therefore lead an absolute ban over HET as this medical “necessity” or “interest” does not exist in the use of these technologies for human enhancement.

However, the legal requirement for this medical “necessity” or “interest” is lifted in certain cases: those pertaining to plastic surgery, which French jurisprudence has identified as “medical and surgical acts with an aesthetical aim”. This practice is heavily regulated, including the premises in which they may be undertaken. Furthermore, the consent requirements are heavier than they are for medical and surgical acts with a therapeutic finality. However, in cases of medical accidents related to an intervention with an aesthetical finality, French law does grant financial compensation to the patient (or client) as it is the case for an intervention with a therapeutic finality. In relation to the protection of the augmented or modified body, some experts argue that it is key to identify the final aim of the enhancement. Whether it is to gain advantage over others or to improve life for the society as a whole does a make difference in terms of the way these technologies may be regulated.

A final argument present in the legal academic literature related to HETs in France that is noteworthy is the one that proposes a ban of all these technologies on the ground that they simply constitute a form of eugenics.

List of tables

- **Table 1:** List of acronyms/abbreviations

List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
HE	Human Enhancement
HET	Human Enhancement Technologies
CCNE	National Ethics Consultative Committee (Comité National Consultatif d’Ethique)

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

1. Introduction

This report aims at presenting currently existing legal regulations of Human Enhancement Technologies (HETs) in France. It does so in two parts. Firstly, it provides a discussion of relevant national legal developments over the past five to ten years as well as the current debate in the legal scholarship regarding HETs in France. The second part seeks to answer specific legal questions that are posed by enhancing technologies. This report draws from a literature review conducted on analyses produced by legal experts on human enhancement in France over the past five to ten years. This report presents French positive law, i.e. the law as it currently exists in France, but also engages with HETs' legal experts on "prospective law", i.e. a form of "juridical sciences fiction".¹

2. Scope and limitations of the report

This report focuses on human enhancement technologies (HETs). In France, the notion of "*Homme augmenté*", i.e. augmented man, is the one used most frequently in order to refer to the use of new technologies for enhancement purposes. The term "*humain augmenté*", "augmented human", which the authors of this report prefer considering its gender neutrality, is also used. However, the notion of human enhancement does not have a large presence in the French society today. As it was already noted in the research on national ethics committees and ethical codes (French report 3.3), the French debate on human enhancement tends to be approached through the notion of "transhumanism".² As a result, the debate on this topic tends to be ideological and generate naïve and radical positioning either for or against this ideology. The weak presence of the notion of "human enhancement" can also be observed in the legal sector in which only few legal experts are exploring issues related to these technologies.

Another notion that is being used to refer to HETs and that should be mentioned here is that of "anthropotechny". It has been coined by Jérôme Goffette to name "an art or a technique of extra-medical transformation of the human being through an intervention on his or her body" that aims "not at restoring the normal state but at bringing about a state that is above the normal, a modified condition that is supposed to answer to a variety of our demands: to be more beautiful, stronger, more intelligent, etc."³ This notion of anthropotechny has also been developed around the same time by the Belgian bioethicist Gilbert Hottois and the German philosopher Peter Sloterdijk and has the advantage of being purely descriptive, hence value-neutral, as opposed to "human enhancement" which is

¹ Pierre-Jérôme Delage, *Cybrides, transgènes et lois bioéthiques*, <https://droitetsf.hypotheses.org/34>, mai 2017, (accessed on 12 October 2018).

² See for instance: Laurent Alexandre et Jean-Michel Besnier, *Les robots font-ils l'amour? Le transhumanisme en 12 questions*, Paris, Dunod, 2016 ; Marie-Christine Piatti, « Vers le transhumanisme - Mythe (la lune) et réalité (le doigt)! » dans Alexandra Bensamoun (ed.), *Les Robots. Objects scientifiques, objets de droits*, Sceaux, Mare & Martin, 2016, p.

³ Jérôme Goffette, *Naissance de l'anthropotechnie. De la médecine au modelage de l'humain*, Paris, Vrin, 2008, p. 69 and 9. Translation by the authors of this report. French version: "un art ou une technique de transformation extra-médicale de l'être humain par intervention sur son corps », qui vise « non plus la restauration de l'état normal, mais l'instauration d'un état surnormal, d'une condition modifiée censée répondre à nos demandes multiples : être plus beau, plus fort, plus intelligent, etc."

positively loaded.⁴ This is the notion that is used in the 2010 National Assembly report on the revision of the Bioethics laws.⁵ The authors of this report have made sure to include all these terms in their research so as to avoid missing relevant information.

Furthermore, this report is to be read in conjunction with the two other reports produced as part of the same research project SIENNA, related to the legal context in France on artificial intelligence and robotics (task 4.2) and human genomics (task 2.2). Indeed, legal questions touching HETs are interconnected with those related to these other emerging technologies. This is particularly clear for instance on topics such as the android or the cyborg.⁶

3. Part I: Summary of legal developments and an analysis of national legal scholarship

This first part summarises key legal developments in relation to HETs in France over the last 5 to 10 years. It also proposes an analysis of the recent national legal scholarship in relation to this technology. For this research, the authors have conducted a desk-based review by going through various search engines, including google, the general catalogue of Sciences Po library and the online catalogue Dalloz which is the primary resource for legal scholarship in France. A variety of search terms were used including, “*humain augmenté*”, “*Homme augmenté*”, “*augmentation de l’Homme*”, “*transhumanisme*”, “*anthropocentrie*” associated with either “*droit*” (“law”) or “*régulation*”. Below is a synthesis of this research.

3.1. Legal developments

HET’s are not explicitly regulated in French law. This is particularly clear when considering the national debate that took place in 2018 in relation to the revision of the 1994 bioethics law. Though one of the key objectives of this revision was to engage with recent technological developments related to medical practices and research, the actual notion of human enhancement is rather surprisingly absent. For instance in the 2018 report published by the National Ethics Committee for the Health and Life Sciences (CCNE) that synthesizes the public debate that took place, HETs are only briefly mentioned in relation to the topics of neurosciences and IA and robotics and rapidly associated to transhumanism.⁷ Nonetheless, some already existing regulations might be relevant to these technologies. A particularly relevant set of laws is the law of bioethics – which in France refer to a set of hard laws. These have been promulgated in 1994 with the creation of three laws:

⁴ Goffette, “Humanité Augmentée, Anthropotechnie: Enjeux Majeurs et Perspectives Humaines”, Public intervention to the National Surgery Academy, 2018.

⁵ Alain Claeys et Jean Leonetti, *Rapport d’information fait au nom de la mission d’information sur la révision des lois de bioéthique*, Paris, Assemblée Nationale, 2010.

⁶ The interrelated nature of legal issues relative to these technologies is made particularly clear in the following article: Xavier Labbé, « L’androïde, le cyborg et les lois bioéthiques », *Les Petites Affiches*, mai 2011, vol. 105, p. 7.

⁷ National Ethics Consultative Committee for life and health sciences (CCNE), *Bioéthique Etats généraux. Rapport de synthèse du Comité Consultatif National d’Ethique. Opinions du comité citoyen*, s.l., CCNE, 2018.

- Law n° 94-548 of the 1 July 1994 related to the treatment of data in health related research, modifying the law n° 78-17 of 6 January 1978 related to information technology, files and liberties;⁸
- Law n° 94-653 of the 29 July 1994 related to respect of the human body;⁹
- Law n° 94-654 of the 29 July 1994 related to the donation and the use of human body elements and products, to medical assistance for procreation and prenatal screening.¹⁰

The bioethics law was revised in 2004 with the law n° 2004-800 related to bioethics. This law established the Biomedicine agency (*Agence de biomédecine*) and decided for a revision of the bioethics law every five years. Hence, the bioethics law was revised again in 2011 with the law n° 2011-814 of the 7 July 2011.¹¹ The last revision process was initiated in 2018 with a large national debate organised by the National Ethics Consultative Committee (CCNE).¹²

The report published by the National Assembly in 2010 as part of the revision process that led to the 2011 law included a section the perspective of the convergence of technologies and related challenges for the bioethics of tomorrow,¹³ including a section on transhumanism.¹⁴ The revision process that took place in 2018 also showed some concern for HETs related issues.¹⁵

Developments in HETS have not led to any modification of the constitution itself which has seen only 22 revisions since it was proclaimed in 1958. However, some of the legal developments described above have relevance to fundamental rights.

3.2. Legal scholarship

To begin with, and as mentioned above, it is important to recognise the fact that HETs have received little interest by French legal experts, in particular due to the ideologically loaded nature of the debate on these technologies in France that are immediately linked to transhumanism. The French population's defiance toward this ideology is reflected in the legal literature that does not give HETs much attention. Nonetheless, there are a number of publications on this topic that are noteworthy. The list below mentions the main ones that were found as part of the literature review conducted for this research.

⁸ Accessible online at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000547135&dateText>

⁹ Accessible online at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000549619&dateText>

¹⁰ Accessible online at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000549618&dateText>

¹¹ These details come from the brief history of the bioethics law presented on the Documentation Française website : <http://www.ladocumentationfrancaise.fr/dossiers/bioethique/historique-lois-bioethique.shtml> (accessed 26 October 2018).

¹² The public debate was centralised by a website: "Bioéthique: Etats généraux 2018": <https://etatsgenerauxdelabioethique.fr> (accessed 26 October 2018).

¹³ A. Claeys et J. Leonetti, *Rapport d'information fait au nom de la mission d'information sur la révision des lois de bioéthique*, *op. cit.*, p. 458-472.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 463-464.

¹⁵ National Ethics Consultative Committee for life and health sciences (CCNE), *Bioéthique Etats généraux. Rapport de synthèse du Comité Consultatif National d'Ethique. Opinions du comité citoyen, op. cit.*

- Aludaat-Dujardin, C. (2015) 'Médecin ou mécanicien? Une approche cybernétique de la pratique médicale en Droit', in Labbé, X. (ed), *L'homme augmenté face au droit*, Villeneuve d'Ascq, Presses Universitaires du Septentrion, pp. 63–70.
- Delage, P.-J. (ed.) (2013) *Science-fiction et science juridique*, IRJS Editions.
- Goffette, J. (2013) 'De l'humain réparé à l'humain augmenté: naissance de l'anthropotechnie', in Kleinpeter, E. (ed), *L'humain augmenté*, CNRS Editions, Paris, pp. 85–106.
- Hilger, G. (2015) 'L'homme augmenté et la responsabilité civile', in Labbé, X. (ed), *L'homme augmenté face au droit*, Villeneuve d'Ascq, Presses Universitaires du Septentrion, pp. 79–110.
- Hirsch, E. and Hirsch, F. (2018) *Traité de bioéthique (IV) Les Nouveaux territoires de la bioéthique*, Paris, Erès.
- Jourdain, P., (2014) 'Les actes de chirurgie esthétique sont des "actes de soins"', *RTD civ.*, p. 394.
- Labbé, P. (2015) 'L'homme augmenté à l'épreuve de la distinction des personnes et des choses', in Labbé, X. (ed), *L'homme augmenté face au droit*, Villeneuve d'Ascq, Presses Universitaires du Septentrion, pp. 41–49.
- Labbé, X. (2011) 'L'androïde, le cyborg et les lois bioéthiques', *Les Petites Affiches*, vol. 105, p. 7.
- Labbé, X. (ed.) (2015) *L'homme augmenté face au droit*, Villeneuve d'Ascq, Presses Universitaires du Septentrion.
- Labbé, X. (2013) 'Le cyborg et les lois de bioéthiques', in Delage, P.-J. (ed), *Droit et science-fiction*, IRJS Editions.
- Nevejans, N. (2017) *Traité de droit et d'éthique de la robotique civile*, Bordeaux, LEH Edition.
- Piatti, M.-C. (2016) 'Vers le transhumanisme - Mythe (la lune) et réalité (le doigt)!', in Bensamoun, A. (ed), *Les Robots. Objects scientifiques, objets de droits*, Sceaux, Mare & Martin.
- Roets, D. (2015) 'Réprimer pénalement les interventions biotechniques à finalité transhumaniste?', in Labbé, X. (ed), *L'homme augmenté face au droit*, Villeneuve d'Ascq, Presses Universitaires du Septentrion, pp. 131–146.
- Sargos, P., (2012) 'Le centenaire jurisprudentiel de la chirurgie esthétique : permanences de fond, dissonances factuelles et prospective', *Recueil Dalloz*, p. 2903.

We provide a brief overview of these legal academic developments below.

The legal experts Xavier Labbé and Pascal Labbé are among the few French jurists who have grappled with the legal regulation of HETs. Xavier Labbé edited one of the rare books on the topic: *L'homme augmenté face au droit* (2015) which is made of the proceedings of a conference he organised. Pascal and Xavier Labbé primarily approach the topic of HETs through a key legal distinction, the one between the person, i.e. the subject of rights, and the thing or object. Pascal Labbé particularly insists on the need to keep this distinction clear when engaging with issues related to the "*Homme augmenté*" – which is the term he uses. As he demonstrates, the body falls within the category of the object. However, it is not any kind of object as it "envelops" the person.¹⁶ Hence the body belongs to the juridical category of objects; it is like an "accessory" put to the service of the person.¹⁷

¹⁶ Pascal Labbé, « L'homme augmenté à l'épreuve de la distinction des personnes et des choses » dans Xavier Labbé (ed.), *L'homme augmenté face au droit*, Villeneuve d'Ascq, Presses Universitaires du Septentrion, 2015, p. 44.

¹⁷ X. Labbé, « L'androïde, le cyborg et les lois bioéthiques », art cit.

According to Xavier Labbée who has also written on the topic, this distinction makes it possible to draw a very strict line between the android and the cyborg: while the former will always remain an object, the latter is a subject of right.¹⁸ Indeed, the cyborg has a “soul” which, in the language of the law, corresponds to being a “subject” according to Pascal Labbée.¹⁹ On the basis of this distinction, Xavier Labbée identifies the status of the prosthetics or other objects linked to the body for enhancement purposes. According to him, though the development of technologies will make it increasingly difficult to distinguish persons from objects, he argues that, even enhanced, the body remains a simple accessory of the person, not the other way around.²⁰

Another important academic author on the legal regulation of HETs in France today is Pierre-Jérôme Delage who published the proceedings of a conference that took place in 2011 under the name *Science-fiction et science juridique* which presents a number of key aspects of the law of HETs in France today. Delage is particularly prone to exploring legal regulation of technologies that are not yet developed, as it is clear in his blog entitled “Law and science fiction”.²¹

A body of legal literature exploring ways to ban and/or punish human enhancement or transhumanism under criminal law is also to be highlighted in the French literature. According to the authors of the present report, this reflects the strongly ideologically loaded nature of the debate on HETs today in France, including in the legal sector. According to Damien Roetz for instance, transhumanism constitutes “threats to the human specie [...] breaching essential values of our democratic societies (freedom and equality).”²² Roetz proposes to introduce in criminal law a crime that specifically covers human enhancement.²³ To him, the basis of this ban would rest, not so much on the principle of human dignity, but rather, in the words of Mireille Delmas-Marty which he quotes, in the “principle of equal belonging to the human community”.²⁴ He argues that the risk of bringing about a society divided in two categories, or even “species”, of human beings is the main reason why these technologies should be banned and heavily penalised. To him, transhumanism is a new form of eugenics.²⁵ Nonetheless, this perspective rests upon the idea of a firm distinction between enhancement and treatment which is increasingly difficult to determine. Similarly, Nathalie Nevejans proposes an analysis of the different propositions made for penal sanctions in relation to human enhancement activities.²⁶

Finally, it is interesting to note that on 22 June 2017 at the Palais de justice in Paris took place an event called “the trial of transhumanism” organised by French lawyers and legal academic experts.²⁷

4. Part II: Analysis of specific legal issues

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ P. Labbée, « L’homme augmenté à l’épreuve de la distinction des personnes et des choses », art cit, p. 44.

²⁰ X. Labbée, « L’androïde, le cyborg et les lois bioéthiques », art cit.

²¹ Blog “Droit et science-fiction”: <https://droitetsf.hypotheses.org>

²² Damien Roetz, « Réprimer pénalement les interventions biotechniques à finalité transhumaniste? » dans Xavier Labbée (ed.), *L’homme augmenté face au droit*, Villeneuve d’Ascq, Presses Universitaires du Septentrion, 2015, p. 135. “menaces sur l’espèce humaine (...) constituant autant d’atteintes à des valeurs essentielles de nos sociétés démocratiques (la liberté et l’égalité).

²³ *Ibid.*, p. 143.

²⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 138. Original in French: “principe d’égal appartenance à la communauté humaine”.

²⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 141.

²⁶ Nathalie Nevejans, *Traité de droit et d’éthique de la robotique civile*, Bordeaux, LEH Edition, 2017, p. 1144-1147.

²⁷ Pierre Sirinelli, « Le Procès du transhumanisme », *Dalloz IP/IT*, 2017, p. 353.

4.1. Terminology and legal demarcations

QUESTION: Does the domestic law in your country provide a legal definition of “health” or the state of “health”?

French law does not provide a specific legal definition of health. However, legal texts generally refer to the definition provided by the WHO.

QUESTION: What are the basic legal terms and demarcations used nationally that should be taken into consideration in the discussion on the regulation of HET?

There are a number of articles in French law insisting on the requirement of a *therapeutic purpose* for an intervention on the human body. The specific articles that express this requirement, include the following:

- In Art. 16-3 Civil Code: “There may be no infringement of the integrity of the human body except in case of **medical necessity for the person** or exceptionally in the **therapeutic interest of another**. The consent of the interested person concerned must be obtained beforehand, except when his condition necessitates a **therapeutic intervention** to which he is not able to assent.”²⁸
- Article R. 4127-8 of the Public health code mentions that the doctor: “must [...] limit his or her prescriptions and acts to what is **necessary for the quality, the safety, and the efficiency of the treatment**”.²⁹ Here, the law makes it clear that it must have a finality of treatment (“soins”).
- Article R. 4127-40 of the Public health code mentions that: “The doctor must forbid him/herself, whether in the diagnostics or in the investigations or interventions that he/she conducts, as well as in the therapies that he/she prescribe, to subject the patient to an **unjustified risk**.”³⁰

However, as developed further below in Section 4.2, medical or surgical acts for aesthetic finality are permitted. The jurisprudence has approached these as “**medical and surgical acts with an aesthetical aim**”.³¹

Terminology relevant to this area of questions has also been developed in relation to compensation measures in cases of faults by the doctor. Art. L. 1142-1 of the public health code determines the

²⁸ Official translation by Legifrance (prepared by David Gruning, 2013), available from the Legifrance website at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/Traductions/en-English/Legifrance-translations> Original version in French: “Il ne peut être porté atteinte à l'intégrité du corps humain qu'en cas de nécessité thérapeutique pour la personne. Le consentement de l'intéressé doit être recueilli préalablement hors le cas où son état rend nécessaire une intervention thérapeutique à laquelle il n'est pas à même de consentir.”

²⁹ Except for the Civil code for which we refer to the official translation provided by Legifrance, translation from other texts are from the authors of this report. Original French version: “doit [...] limiter ses prescriptions et ses actes à ce qui est nécessaire à la qualité, à la sécurité et à l'efficacité des soins.”

³⁰ Original French version: “Le médecin doit s'interdire, dans les investigations et interventions qu'il pratique comme dans les thérapeutiques qu'il prescrit, de faire courir au patient un risque injustifié.”

³¹ Pierre Sargos, « Le centenaire jurisprudentiel de la chirurgie esthétique : permanences de fond, dissonances factuelles et prospective », *Recueil Dalloz*, 2012, sect. 7.

regime of compensation for “acts of prevention, diagnostic or treatment”.³² In an important decision, the Court of cassation (5 February 2014, n° 12-29.140) assessed that acts of plastic surgery could be recognised as a medical act as defined in the art. L. 1142 and could therefore benefit from compensations in case of negligence on the part of the practitioner.³³ As Jourdain notes, “actes de soins” – **acts of care** – are generally understood in a large sense of the term and come to include all acts that imply medical or surgical techniques.³⁴ As he puts it, the assimilation of non-curative acts to acts of care (“*actes de soins*”) is generally justified by the fact that they are **acts “realised by healthcare professionals, within a medical context and through the means of medical or surgical techniques”**.³⁵ As such, it could be considered “discriminatory” to distinguish, in cases of accidents, between acts that were conducted with a therapeutic finality and those for whom this finality was absent.³⁶ Hence, both benefit from financial compensations as provided by the National office for the indemnisation of medical accident (ONIAM).

Furthermore, the need for medical or therapeutic finality is required for an exemption of the payment of the VAT. As an official document from the tax office put it in 2012, acts are VAT exempted only if “they consist in providing a care to the patient, i.e. when they pursue a **therapeutic finality**.”³⁷

QUESTION: What criteria are used to classify services, devices and products according to those categories?

The Civil code distinguishes the “body”, its “elements” (“*éléments*”) and its “products” (“*produits*”) in Art. 16-1. The 3rd paragraph of this article (coming from the bioethics law of the 23 July 1994) specifies that “the human body, its elements and its products may not form the object of a patrimonial right”.³⁸ However, as Aludaat-Dujardin makes it clear, “prostheses, manufactured objects and material elements for the human body, can be commercialised.”³⁹

Aludaat-Dujardin specifies that in the Public health code, “medical prosthesis or dispositive is identified as a ‘medical product’. The term of ‘product’ reflects the very nature of the prosthesis, a thing (or ‘res’) that may of course be commercialised.”⁴⁰

³² Original version in French: “actes de prévention, de diagnostic ou de soins”

³³ Patrice Jourdain, « Les actes de chirurgie esthétique sont des “actes de soins” », *RTD civ.*, 2014, p. 394.

³⁴ Quoted in *Ibid.* Translated by the authors of the present report. Original version in French: « Mais attendu que les actes de chirurgie esthétique, quand ils sont réalisés dans les conditions prévues aux articles L. 6322-1 et L. 6322-2 du code de la santé publique, ainsi que les actes médicaux qui leur sont préparatoires, constituent des actes de soins au sens de l'article L. 1142-1 du même code ».

³⁵ *Ibid.*

³⁶ *Ibid.*

³⁷ Patrice Jourdain, « Les actes de chirurgie esthétique sont des “actes de soins” », *RTD civ.*, 2014, p. 394.

³⁸ “Le corps humain, ses éléments et ses produits ne peuvent faire l'objet d'un droit patrimonial.”

³⁹ Céline Aludaat-Dujardin, « Médecin ou mécanicien? Une approche cybernétique de la pratique médicale en Droit » dans Xavier Labbé (ed.), *L'homme augmenté face au droit*, Villeneuve d'Ascq, Presses Universitaires du Septentrion, 2015, p. 64. “les prothèses, objets manufacturés et éléments matériels du corps humain, peuvent faire l'objet d'un commerce.”

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 65. Our translation; original version in French: “Dans le Code de la santé publique, la prothèse ou dispositif médical demeure bel et bien qualifiée de ‘produit médical’. Le terme de ‘produit’ renvoie irréductiblement à la nature même de la prothèse, chose (ou ‘res’) bien évidemment susceptible d’être commercialisée. »

4.2 Right to integrity of the person, legal permissibility of non-therapeutic services on the human body

QUESTION: Does the domestic law recognize the right to (physical and/or mental) integrity of the person? If yes, please provide a relevant citation. What are the limits to this right? Please provide examples. What criteria and values are considered to set those limits?

The protection of integrity of the person in French law is key. It appears primarily in art. 16 and following of the Civil code:⁴¹

- Art. 16: "Legislation ensures the primacy of the person, prohibits any infringement of the latter's **dignity**, and guarantees **respect** for the human being from the outset of his life."⁴²
- Art. 16.1: "Everyone has the **right to respect for his body**. The human body is **inviolable**. The human body, its elements, and its products may not form the object of a patrimonial right."⁴³
- Art. 16.1.1: "The respect owed to the human body does not end with death. The remains of a deceased person, including the ashes of one whose body has been cremated, must be treated with respect, dignity, and decency."⁴⁴
- Art. 16.2: "The judge may prescribe any measure appropriate to prevent or end an illicit infringement of the human body or illicit actions relating to its elements or products, even after death."⁴⁵

There are two exceptions to this right to integrity of the human body, as specified in art. 16.3 of the Civil code: "There may be no infringement of the integrity of the human body except in case of **medical necessity for the person** or exceptionally in the **therapeutic interest of another**." In any case, "consent of the interested person concerned must be obtained beforehand, except when his condition necessitates a therapeutic intervention to which he is not able to assent."⁴⁶ This restriction of the right to infringe on the integrity of the human body only in case of medical necessity can also be found in the art. 41 of the Medical deontology code according to which "no mutilating intervention may be conducted without a very serious medical objective and, except in cases of emergency or impossibility, without informing the person and without his or her consent."⁴⁷

⁴¹ Legifrance translation (by David Gruning, 2013), available from the Legifrance website at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/Traductions/en-English/Legifrance-translations>

⁴² "La loi assure la primauté de la personne, interdit toute atteinte à la dignité de celle-ci et garantit le respect de l'être humain dès le commencement de sa vie."

⁴³ "Chacun a droit au respect de son corps. Le corps humain est inviolable. Le corps humain, ses éléments et ses produits ne peuvent faire l'objet d'un droit patrimonial."

⁴⁴ "Le respect dû au corps humain ne cesse pas avec la mort. Les restes des personnes décédées, y compris les cendres de celles dont le corps a donné lieu à crémation, doivent être traités avec respect, dignité et décence."

⁴⁵ "Le juge peut prescrire toutes mesures propres à empêcher ou faire cesser une atteinte illicite au corps humain ou des agissements illicites portant sur des éléments ou des produits de celui-ci, y compris après la mort."

⁴⁶ Original version in French: "Il ne peut être porté atteinte à l'intégrité du corps humain qu'en cas de **nécessité thérapeutique** pour la personne. Le **consentement** de l'intéressé doit être recueilli préalablement hors le cas où son état rend nécessaire une intervention thérapeutique à laquelle il n'est pas à même de consentir."

⁴⁷ Translation by the authors of this report. Original version in French: "Aucune intervention mutilante ne peut être pratiquée sans motif médical très sérieux et, sauf urgence ou impossibilité, sans information de l'intéressé et sans son consentement."

Furthermore, we may note that French law also protects the integrity of the human species itself in Art. 16-4 of the Civil code: “No one may infringe upon the integrity of mankind. Any eugenic practice which aims at organizing the selection of persons is forbidden. Any medical procedure whose purpose is to cause the birth of a child genetically identical to another person alive or dead is forbidden. Without prejudice to any research that aims at preventing and treating genetic diseases, there may be no transformation of genes in order to alter the descent of a person.”⁴⁸

QUESTION: How is the legality of enhancement procedures (understood as non-therapeutic interventions in the human body) established?

Hence, a number of articles in French law prohibit doctors from engaging in medical acts that have no therapeutic purposes. For this reason, according to the philosopher Jérôme Goffette, an expert in human enhancement – which he calls “anthropotechny” – “medical deontology cannot accept anthropotechnical techniques as they are contrary to it.”⁴⁹ Similarly, as the National Assembly report specifies, considering that enhancement procedures do not respond to situations of suffering or distress, doctors should not engage in them.⁵⁰

However, medical or surgical acts for an aesthetical finality are allowed in France. In a landmark case, the 1913 Calou judgement, the court of appeal of Paris determined that the finality of a medical act is not necessarily to treat an illness but can also be to hide a “physical imperfection”. This case judged the doctor responsible for the harm his intervention caused.⁵¹ However, it is not before 1996 that the legal status of plastic surgery was clarified with the judgement of the 17 October 1996 related to the publicity of the prices of medical and surgical acts with aesthetical finality. Law n° 2002-303 of the 4 March 2002 provided the necessary legal regulatory framework with the art. L. 6322-1, 2 and 3 and the implementation decree (art. R. 6322-1 to 48). Art. L. 1151-2 of the Public health code concerns the prevention of risks related to “acts, procedures, techniques and methods with an aesthetics aim.”⁵²

QUESTION: Are there limits to what non-therapeutic procedures can be performed on a human body? What criteria are used to establish those limits? What is the role of consent? Does the national law, case-law or legal doctrine provide any guidance on how risks and benefits of non-therapeutic procedures should be weighed and/or what is the acceptable level of risk in those cases? Is there a legal requirement for informed consent in the case of all non-therapeutic procedures? If yes, are requirements concerning informed consent more or less rigorous than in the case of procedures

⁴⁸ Original version in French: “Nul ne peut porter atteinte à l'intégrité de l'espèce humaine. Toute pratique eugénique tendant à l'organisation de la sélection des personnes est interdite. Est interdite toute intervention ayant pour but de faire naître un enfant génétiquement identique à une autre personne vivante ou décédée. Sans préjudice des recherches tendant à la prévention et au traitement des maladies génétiques, aucune transformation ne peut être apportée aux caractères génétiques dans le but de modifier la descendance de la personne.”

⁴⁹ Jérôme Goffette, *Naissance de l'anthropotechnie. De la médecine au modelage de l'humain*, Paris, Vrin, 2008, p. 143. Original version in French: “la déontologie médicale ne peut pas accepter les pratiques anthropotechniques, car elles lui sont contraires.”

⁵⁰ A. Claeys et J. Leonetti, *Rapport d'information fait au nom de la mission d'information sur la révision des lois de bioéthique*, *op. cit.*, p. 471.

⁵¹ P. Sargos, « Le centenaire jurisprudentiel de la chirurgie esthétique : permanences de fond, dissonances factuelles et prospective », *art cit.*, p. 15.

⁵² *Ibid.* Authors' translation. Original version in French: “actes, procédés, techniques et méthodes à visée esthétique”.

with a therapeutic aim?

Medical and surgical acts with an aesthetical aim are very strictly regulated in the law and may lead to criminal sanctions for breaches of the law.⁵³ The fact that there is no therapeutic necessity leads to stronger requirements in terms of the information that the practitioner needs to provide to the patient. Jurisprudence points to the need for “a very large information” of the patient in cases of a medical or surgical intervention that is to be conducted for an aesthetical finality.⁵⁴ This jurisprudence is confirmed by art. L. 6322-2 of the public health code (issued from the law of 4 March 2002), that requires the practitioner to give the patient, and if necessary, the person in charge of the patient, information on the conditions of the intervention, its risks, and the potential consequences and complications. Furthermore, the information must come together with a quote (that includes a note on the fact that VAT applies, contrary to medical acts with a medical finality). According to art. 6322-30, there must be 15 days between the date of issuance of the quote and the actual intervention. As indicated by Sargos, the French society for Plastic, Reconstructive and Aesthetics Surgery (SoFCPRE) has developed information sheets to provide patients with the necessary information.⁵⁵ Hence, due to the fact that there is no “medical necessity”, there is even more importance given to the information to be provided to the patient in order to ensure his/her informed consent.

In addition, the premises where these acts may take place are regulated: they must be accredited in conditions defined in art. L. 6113-3 of the public health code and authorised by the departmental prefect. In addition, it is forbidden to advertise plastic surgery interventions.

QUESTION: Has the question about the protection afforded to the augmented or modified body (e.g. body with prosthetics) been addressed nationally? Is the augmented or modified body afforded the same protection and guarantees as an organic body? Are there issues about ownership?

Bioethics law does not define the prosthesis nor its regulatory framework. According to Xavier Labbée, there are no reason to consider these objects “sacred”, as is the human body. Indeed, they are made by human beings and have value only in terms of their functionality.⁵⁶ A key terminological distinction in the legal debate related to the regulation of HETs that has relevance in relation to the protection of the augmented body is the **status of the person and his/her body**. This distinction is at the core of the legal analysis proposed by Pascal Labbée and Xavier Labbée on human enhancement in France today. As mentioned above, while the “person” is the subject of rights, the body is an object of right. However, as it “envelops” the person, the body is not like any object.⁵⁷ as Pascal Labbée puts it, the 1994 bioethics law have made it a “**sacred**” object.⁵⁸ This sacredness reflects the notion of “human dignity” that is present in art. 16 of the Civil code and leads to an obligation to protect it.⁵⁹

It is on the basis of this definition of the person and the body that Labbée then defines the status of the implant. For this, Labbée relies upon a legal distinction between the “**person by nature**” (“*personne par nature*”) and the “**person by destination**” (“*personne par destination*”). This distinction

⁵³ *Ibid.*

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵⁵ These can be found online at : <http://www.plasticiciens.fr/?p=31> (page accessed 27 october 2018).

⁵⁶ Xavier Labbée, « L’homme augmenté », *Recueil Dalloz*, 2012, p. 2323.

⁵⁷ P. Labbée, « L’homme augmenté à l’épreuve de la distinction des personnes et des choses », art cit, p. 44.

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

⁵⁹ *Ibid.*

has been established 30 years ago by the tribunal of Lille. The **implant** becomes a “person by nature” and will be regulated by the regime of the person and the human body to which it is incorporated.⁶⁰ On the contrary, **removable prostheses** have been qualified by the Lille tribunal as “person by destination”. As such, the removable instrument is considered as the person insofar as it is associated to him or her.⁶¹ Labbé specifies that, if the instrument is separated from his or her owner, then it becomes again an object in the legal sense of the term. As such, for instance, a denture that is taken away while still in the mouth of the person will be considered as an offence against a person; on the contrary, a denture that is stolen while removed from the mouth will be considered as a property-related offence.⁶²

According to Pascal Labbé, it is urgent to define, within the regime of things, the status of the enhancing prostheses.⁶³ To him, insofar as these prostheses might have for finality only to satisfy individual or collective desires to be the best, then they should not receive any particular status.⁶⁴

He concludes arguing that, considering that property law determines what is “sacred” and what is not, what can be sold and what cannot be, what is public and what is not, what is regulated and what is not”, it should also determine “who can possess (or be implemented) a certain object and who cannot.”⁶⁵

An additional proof of the fact that prostheses belong to property law is the fact that they have a cost, contrary to organs that can only be donated.⁶⁶

5. Discussion and conclusion

On the basis of the overview presented in this report on the legal responses to HETs in France, it can be noted that issues and questions related to these technologies are rather weakly addressed by legal experts. This is primarily due to the ideological approach of the debate that dominates in France. Indeed, discussions on HETs are immediately linked to transhumanism, which is an ideology that the French population rather massively rejects. As such, the new possibilities conferred by emerging HETs are not taken into consideration in and of themselves, and poorly addressed in the academic literature, including in the legal literature.

According to the authors of this report, this is a weakness for the regulation of HETs in France. There is an urgency for legal experts to engage in depth in this issue in order to provide adequate regulatory framework to these issues. The already existing legal approach to plastic surgery which removes the need for a “medical necessity” or the “therapeutic interest of another” to allow for an “infringement of the integrity of the human body (according to art. 16-1 of the civil code) could provide an anchor to engage with the legal regulation of HETs in France. Furthermore, the idea to ban HETs considering the risks that they pose in terms of bringing about a society divided by the enhanced human beings and

⁶⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 46.

⁶¹ *Ibid.*

⁶² *Ibid.*, p. 46-47.

⁶³ *Ibid.*, p. 48.

⁶⁴ *Ibid.*

⁶⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 49.

⁶⁶ C. Aludaat-Dujardin, « Médecin ou mécanicien? Une approche cybernétique de la pratique médicale en Droit », art cit, p. 70.

the non-enhanced should be further developed, in particular in relation to the limits that is to be put to this potential ban.

Annex – Translations

English translations for articles of the Civil Code:

- This report used the official translation proposed by Legifrance (prepared by David Gruning, 2013), available from the Legifrance website at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/Traductions/en-English/Legifrance-translations>.

English translations for articles from other legal texts:

- Translation from other texts are from the authors of this report.

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